

CHOOSING A TRANSPORT UNIT FOR THE TRANSPORTATION OF PERISHABLE GOODS

Fayzullaev Gaybullo Oktamovich, asistent,

Tashkent State transport University

АННОТАЦИЯ В этом тезисе рассматривается выбор и использование транспортного средства с регулируемой температурой при перевозке скоропортящихся грузов. Установлено, что объем и вес перевозимого груза, характер перевозок являются основными факторами при выборе альтернативного вида транспорта.

Ключевые слова: доставка, рефконтейнер, скоропортящиеся грузы, холодильная техника

ANNOTATION This thesis discusses the choice and use of a temperature-controlled vehicle for the transportation of perishable goods. It is established that the volume and weight of the transported cargo, the nature of transportation are the main factors when choosing an alternative mode of transport.

Keywords: delivery, refrigerated container, perishable loads, refrigeration equipment

Transportation of temperature-controlled cargo requires special attention in all types of supply chains. In this transport, the entire supply chain is considered important for those who use, load, unload and process temperature-controlled cargo units (refrigerated refcontainers). The structure of the brochure corresponds to the stages of Transportation. The brochure follows IMO/XMT/UNECE's practice of packaging in freight transport units (gruzovie transportnie yedinisi). Cargo units determine the technology of various participants in the supply chain, which will have to be covered in detail when transporting carrots and pulses. Additional instructions on perishable goods are required to be provided in the

information material on the shipping units. The table below includes several transportation technologies, forming in the modern supply chain.

Today, the demand for temperature-controlled refrigerated containers for the transportation of vegetables and melons continues to grow. The transport chain in these containers is used in the same way as in transport units. In this dissertation, in addition to recommendations and other information about transportation in refrigerated containers, all interested parties indicate the possibility of providing national, regional and international rules for the preparation and transportation of certain goods for transportation, including data records.

Table 1.

Obligations of participants of transportation

	Mainten ance	Cleanin g	Equipme nt placement	Cargo packin g	Stowage during cargo loading	Rationing during transportat ion	The supplie r
Operator	*	*	*			*	
Client				*	*	*	
Packer					*	*	
Shipper			*	*	*	*	
Transporta tion by car						*	*
Transporta tion by railway						*	*
Intermodal operator	*	*	*			*	
Carrier	*	*	*			*	

Load receiver		*				*	*
---------------	--	---	--	--	--	---	---

Traditional refrigerated containers have an operating temperature range from $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (from $22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$ to $86\text{ }^{\circ}\text{F}$), which does not ensure proper temperature distribution in moderate amounts. The desire of shippers to protect cargo during transportation of vegetables and melons has led to the development of special temperature containers capable of maintaining and evenly distributing temperature. A common feature of the proposed refrigerated containers is that they ensure the transportation of cargo in a certain temperature range, and the temperature of the supplied air is constantly monitored and regulated by the container cooler. While modern refrigerator containers can provide a decrease in temperature at certain intervals, refrigerator containers for intermodal transportation, as a rule, are still designed only to maintain the initially set temperature, and not to reduce the temperature of the cargo. Therefore, any frozen product that must be packaged for transportation must be pre-cooled to the desired temperature, and any new product must be cooled to a temperature that ensures the best quality of the product during transfer to the recipient before loading.

When preparing the placement procedure before loading into refrigerated containers, it is necessary to take into account the type of cargo being transported and its volume. For frozen products, if the batch is cooled properly, the function of the refrigeration device is to maintain the temperature of the external surfaces of the goods, despite the heat coming through doors, walls, roofs. This can be achieved by circulating cold air around the load (peripheral circulation). Some cargoes, such as fish, are sometimes transported in bulk (unpacked), and it is very important to pre-cool the cargo to the desired transport temperature. This ensures that the cargo retains its shape and does not deform during loading or transportation, while when using containers, this danger comes from the floor covering. Any deformation of the cargo after packing can reduce the air flow around the cargo. When laying on pallets, the load must be positioned in such a way that

there are no vertical gaps. If this cannot be avoided, the gaps should be closed with packaging material. Refcontainers are the most optimal solution for such requirements.

References

1. Баротов Ж. С., Файзуллаев Ф. Ё. Юкларни етказиб беришда маршрутлаштириш технологик жараёнларни яхшилаш чора-тадбирлари // Results of National Scientific Research International Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 253-261.
2. Ж.С. Баротов, Ф.Ё. Файзуллаев. Темир йўл транспортида маршрутли ташишда унга таъсир этувчи омиллар таҳлили // Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal. – 2022. – №1. 225-230 pp.
3. Ж.С. Баротов, Г.У. Файзуллаев, Д.Б. Жураева. Исследование транзитных грузоперевозок железнодорожным транспортом // Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. Volume-2 Issue-4-2, 2022. 1045-1052 pp.
4. Кобулов Ж. Р., Баротов Ж. С., Ташматова М. С., Файзуллаев Г. У. Разработка мероприятий по развитию транзитного потенциала Акционерного Общества Узбекистон Темир Йуллари в международных грузоперевозках // АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ Учредители: ООО "Институт развития образования и консалтинга". – №. 10. – С. 754-761.
5. Р. Ш. Бозоров, Способы эффективного использования пропускной способности участков в условиях пропуска высокоскоростных пассажирских поездов / М. Х. Расулов, С. Е. Бекжанова, М.Н. Машарипов. – Текст: непосредственный // Железнодорожный транспорт : Актуальные вопросы и инновации. – 2021. – № 2. – С. 5–22.
6. Z.G. Muhamedova, D.Sh. Boboyev. [YUKLARNI YETKAZIB BERISH JARAYONIDA ZAMONAVIY TASHISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNI TADQIQ QILISH](#). Железнодорожный транспорт, <https://educonference.ru/index.php/icts>

1(16), 2022, 16-19. //

https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=hgV11YIAAAAJ&citation_for_view=hgV11YIAAAAJ:UeHWp8X0CEIC

7. Barotov J. S. et al. REFKONTEYNERLARDA TEZ BUZILUVCHAN YUKLARNI TASHISHDA HAVO HARORATINING TO ‘G ‘RI TAQSIMLASH USULLARI //Results of National Scientific Research International Journal. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 181-195.